

Online Appendix for

Hybridization and Transgressive Evolution Generate Diversity in an Adaptive Radiation of *Anolis* Lizards

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A) Quartet Hypothesis Test Simplot

- △ reject tree and star
- fail to reject tree; reject star

B) Neighbor-Net Splits Graph

Fig S1: A simplex plot of quartet hypothesis test results from NANUQ at $\alpha = 10^{-6}$ and $\beta = 0.95$ (A) and the inferred splits graph for the Puerto Rican *Anolis* species (B). The three axes in the plot (black lines) represent tree-like concordance factors. Blue circles indicate quartets consistent with tree-like structure; red triangles indicate quartets for which the hypothesis tests rejected tree-like structure and star structure (unresolved topology), thereby suggesting reticulation. The splits graph was constructed using the Neighbor-Net algorithm on quartet distances. Each set of parallel lines represents one split; reticulations indicate the presence of conflicting signal, which can result from hybridization.

Fig. S2: Phenograms plotting trait values for SVL (A), head length (B), femur length (C), toepad width (D), and tail length (E) across the inferred phylogenetic network. Blue branches represent hybridization events.

Table S1: Sequencing statistics for each re-sequenced *Anolis* genome. Total reads (raw reads) multiplied by read length (150bp after adapter trimming) and divided by an estimated genome size of 1.7Gb provide estimated sequencing depth. Statistics on filtered reads, mapped reads, and average quality score were calculated using the samtools stats and coverage commands.

Species	Sample	Filtered reads	Mapped reads	Average quality	Final mean depth
<i>Anolis cooki</i>	MVZ235170	47983746	40446629	38.9	3.6X
<i>Anolis cristatellus</i>	SRX2159668	80242626	60194962	33.5	5.3X
<i>Anolis cuvieri</i>	IW2556	59926140	47208732	38.5	4.2X
<i>Anolis evermanni</i>	IW2555	24159938	19824875	38.2	1.7X
<i>Anolis gundlachi</i>	IW1322	82175930	61429334	37.2	5.4X
<i>Anolis krugi</i>	IW2414	30026792	24744741	36.2	2.2X
<i>Anolis occultus</i>	IW2455	37432772	27175405	38.5	2.4X
<i>Anolis poncensis</i>	MVZ226166	50212836	42858750	39.1	3.8X
<i>Anolis pulchellus</i>	IW1139	93500244	62003286	37.3	5.5X
<i>Anolis stratulus</i>	IW1319	64997054	49425481	37.3	4.4X
<i>Anolis frenatus</i>	PRJNA400786	48834788	15843937	33.2	1.4X

Table S2: $D_{\min}$ and f_4 -ratio statistics for all species triads, calculated using Dsuite (Malinsky et al. 2021). In these tests, P1 and P2 are sister taxa, and D statistics are calculated based on excess allele sharing between P2 and P3 such that gene flow between P2 and P3 leads to positive D statistics. For each triad, the f_4 -ratio statistic, minimum D statistic across all arrangements ($D_{\min}$), and associated z-score and p-value, after Holm-Bonferroni correction (FWER < 0.001), are presented. Asterisks (*) indicate significantly elevated $D_{\min}$ statistics after correction for multiple tests (Sig).

P1	P2	P3	$D_{\min}$	z-score	f_4-ratio	p (corr.)	Sig
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.1510	16.16	0.0438	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.1479	14.95	0.0440	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.1472	14.45	0.0434	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.1391	19.59	0.0416	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.1342	18.68	0.0412	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.1220	14.29	0.0377	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.1181	9.28	0.0281	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.1118	11.45	0.0324	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.1083	14.14	0.0300	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.1072	8.87	0.0246	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.1056	9.43	0.0243	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.1013	8.31	0.0250	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.1007	15.97	0.0223	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.1005	8.16	0.0211	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0995	9.07	0.0221	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0917	14.66	0.0280	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0916	13.91	0.0203	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0881	14.25	0.0211	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0868	11.14	0.0186	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0863	7.82	0.0291	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0851	9.86	0.0262	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0846	12.05	0.0207	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0844	9.39	0.0252	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0817	11.52	0.0242	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0799	9.50	0.0199	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0792	13.04	0.0231	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0740	11.86	0.0233	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	0.0718	9.26	0.0623	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	0.0704	9.27	0.0253	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0690	8.65	0.0207	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0684	6.93	0.0160	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	0.0657	8.20	0.0393	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0647	7.97	0.0217	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	0.0646	8.07	0.0435	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0641	9.40	0.0193	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	0.0636	7.12	0.0388	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	0.0628	8.32	0.0355	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	0.0614	6.93	0.0358	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*

P1	P2	P3	D_{min}	z-score	f₄-ratio	p (corr.)	Sig
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	0.0612	7.33	0.0269	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0602	8.17	0.0128	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0568	7.98	0.0156	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	0.0559	10.11	0.0377	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0557	6.44	0.0132	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	0.0555	8.06	0.0245	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	0.0548	10.20	0.0243	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	0.0536	7.34	0.0331	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0520	6.13	0.0108	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0519	5.06	0.0107	0.00002	*
<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	0.0518	9.61	0.0353	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0512	4.34	0.0110	0.00080	*
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0488	6.14	0.0135	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	0.0430	5.77	0.0389	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	0.0414	5.11	0.0276	0.00002	*
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0398	4.92	0.0130	0.00005	*
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	0.0390	7.54	0.0251	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	0.0388	4.42	0.0341	0.00056	*
<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	0.0383	3.84	0.0242	0.00636	
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	0.0355	6.22	0.0208	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0351	5.93	0.0117	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	0.0351	5.95	0.0280	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. cuvieri</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0329	7.01	0.0132	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	0.0320	4.91	0.0181	0.00005	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0318	3.79	0.0096	0.00730	
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0317	4.20	0.0068	0.00138	
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	0.0315	3.67	0.0169	0.01154	
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	0.0308	8.76	0.0225	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	0.0304	5.44	0.0270	3.434x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0304	3.06	0.0065	0.08637	
<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	0.0303	7.43	0.0320	<1x10 ⁻⁶	*
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	0.0300	3.14	0.0220	0.07009	
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	0.0292	4.30	0.0141	0.00095	*
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0290	3.15	0.0061	0.06965	
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	0.0281	3.44	0.0159	0.02607	
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0280	3.44	0.0087	0.02607	
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	0.0269	2.72	0.0106	0.23193	
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	0.0268	4.29	0.0140	0.00099	*
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	0.0233	3.80	0.0101	0.00718	
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	0.0232	3.14	0.0123	0.07009	
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	0.0229	5.22	0.0131	0.00001	*
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	0.0227	4.26	0.0117	0.00108	
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0226	3.60	0.0066	0.01451	
<i>A. occultus</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	0.0223	3.27	0.0075	0.04611	
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	0.0214	3.78	0.0125	0.00768	

P1	P2	P3	D_{min}	z-score	f₄-ratio	p (corr.)	Sig
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	0.0209	1.86	0.0145	1.00000	
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	0.0208	2.84	0.0149	0.16383	
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0200	2.07	0.0062	1.00000	
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	0.0192	2.40	0.0152	0.53722	
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	0.0177	2.85	0.0082	0.16383	
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0172	2.22	0.0040	0.76220	
<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	0.0171	2.33	0.0111	0.63442	
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0159	2.24	0.0034	0.76220	
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0148	1.68	0.0031	1.00000	
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0146	2.28	0.0047	0.69695	
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0146	2.00	0.0062	1.00000	
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	0.0135	2.12	0.0076	0.96178	
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0132	2.71	0.0030	0.23193	
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0129	1.25	0.0029	1.00000	
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	0.0122	1.37	0.0055	1.00000	
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	0.0122	1.37	0.0052	1.00000	
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0121	1.37	0.0032	1.00000	
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	0.0115	1.66	0.0044	1.00000	
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	0.0115	2.89	0.0084	0.14504	
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0114	1.60	0.0035	1.00000	
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	0.0113	1.83	0.0064	1.00000	
<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	0.0105	1.75	0.0060	1.00000	
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	0.0088	1.53	0.0056	1.00000	
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	0.0085	1.19	0.0047	1.00000	
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	0.0078	1.09	0.0038	1.00000	
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0077	0.87	0.0025	1.00000	
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	0.0059	0.66	0.0025	1.00000	
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	0.0057	0.65	0.0026	1.00000	
<i>A. occultus</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0054	0.65	0.0016	1.00000	
<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0054	0.63	0.0012	1.00000	
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0049	0.51	0.0011	1.00000	
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	0.0040	0.95	0.0018	1.00000	
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	0.0031	0.50	0.0019	1.00000	
<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	0.0026	0.35	0.0022	1.00000	
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	0.0019	0.31	0.0011	1.00000	
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0015	0.32	0.0006	1.00000	
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	0.0001	0.01	0.0000	1.00000	

Table S3: Branch-specific f_b -statistics (f_b), which capture excess allele sharing between a species and a branch compared to its sister branch, calculated using Dsuite (Malinsky et al. 2021). Values in bold were statistically significant after Holm-Bonferroni correction (FWER < 0.001).

Branch descendants	<i>A. occultus</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>
<i>A. occultus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>A. cuvieri</i> , <i>A. krugi</i> , <i>A. stratulus</i> , <i>A. evermanni</i> , <i>A. cristatellus</i> , <i>A. cooki</i> , <i>A. poncensis</i> , <i>A. gundlachi</i> , <i>A. pulchellus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>A. cuvieri</i>	0.0087	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>A. krugi</i> , <i>A. stratulus</i> , <i>A. evermanni</i> , <i>A. cristatellus</i> , <i>A. cooki</i> , <i>A. poncensis</i> , <i>A. gundlachi</i> , <i>A. pulchellus</i>	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>A. krugi</i>	0.0108	0.0128	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>A. stratulus</i> , <i>A. evermanni</i> , <i>A. cristatellus</i> , <i>A. cooki</i> , <i>A. poncensis</i> , <i>A. gundlachi</i> , <i>A. pulchellus</i>	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>A. stratulus</i> , <i>A. evermanni</i>	0	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>A. stratulus</i>	0	0	0	-	-	0	0	0	0.0125	0.0101
<i>A. evermanni</i>	0.0246	0.0211	0.0388	-	-	0	0.0354	0.0253	0	0
<i>A. cristatellus</i> , <i>A. cooki</i> , <i>A. poncensis</i> , <i>A. gundlachi</i> , <i>A. pulchellus</i>	0	0	0.0689	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>A. cristatellus</i> , <i>A. cooki</i>	0.0068	0	0	0	0.0123	-	-	-	-	-
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	0	0	0	0.0393	0	-	-	0	0.0696	0.0682
<i>A. cooki</i>	0.0300	0.0156	0	0	0.0251	-	-	0.0366	0	0
<i>A. poncensis</i> , <i>A. gundlachi</i> , <i>A. pulchellus</i>	0	0	0.0267	0.0042	0	-	-	-	-	-
<i>A. poncensis</i>	0.0425	0.0212	0.0122	0	0.0428	0	0.0597	-	-	-
<i>A. gundlachi</i> , <i>A. pulchellus</i>	0	0	0	0.0353	0	0.0378	0	-	-	-
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0298	-	-
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	0	0.0030	0.1151	0	0	0.0082	0	0	-	-

Table S4: Overall model scores for the phylogenetic networks inferred using PhyloNet and SNaQ, allowing for different maximum numbers of reticulations (h). Scores are listed as total log probabilities for PhyloNet and as log likelihoods for SNaQ. We calculated the percent change (Pct. Change) for each successive value of h for use with the slope heuristic for selecting the optimal number of reticulations.

Reticulations (h)	PhyloNet		SNaQ	
	Total Log Probability	Pct. Change	Log Likelihood	Pct. Change
0	-204154.89	-	217.060	-
1	-203762.53	0.192%	137.591	36.612%
2	-203642.07	0.059%	112.007	18.594%
3	-203524.33	0.058%	99.945	10.768%
4	-203453.64	0.035%	99.878	0.067%
5	-203428.57	0.012%	99.452	0.427%
6	-	-	99.103	0.351%
7	-	-	99.098	0.005%
8	-	-	99.096	0.002%
9	-	-	99.096	0.000%

Table S5: Likelihood ratio tests (LRTs) of speciation with gene flow for three models: no gene flow following speciation (M_0), a discrete-beta model of decreasing gene flow post-speciation (M_1), and an isolation-with-migration (IM) model with a constant rate of gene flow post-speciation (M_2). Model support was assessed with likelihood ratio tests, and the resulting $2\Delta\ln L$ values were compared against 2 distributions to evaluate statistical significance. For the model comparison of M_1 vs. M_0 , the critical values are $2\Delta\ln L = 2.71$ at $\alpha = 0.05$ and $2\Delta\ln L = 5.41$ at $\alpha = 0.01$, and for M_2 vs. M_0 the critical values are $2\Delta\ln L = 5.99$ for $\alpha = 0.05$ and $2\Delta\ln L = 9.21$ for $\alpha = 0.01$, based on χ^2 distributions with one and two degrees of freedom, respectively. For each species pair, we report the number of loci used in the test (N[loci]), the log-likelihood scores ($\ln L$) for each model, and the LRT scores ($2\Delta\ln L$) for each model comparison; values in bold are statistically significant at $\alpha = 0.01$.

Taxon 1	Taxon 2	N[loci]	$M_0 \ln L$ (no gene flow)	$M_1 \ln L$ (discrete-beta)	$M_2 \ln L$ (isolation-migration)	M_1-M_0 $2\Delta\ln L$	M_2-M_0 $2\Delta\ln L$
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. cooki</i>	1798	-100388.25	-100388.27	-100388.32	-0.0396	-0.1495
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	1798	-121534.01	-121534.00	-121534.08	0.0180	-0.1400
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	1795	-85463.08	-85434.85	-85435.36	56.4568	55.4334
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	1798	-103478.66	-103467.42	-103478.66	22.4984	0.0002
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	1797	-100388.27	-100388.27	-100388.25	-0.0396	-0.1495
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	1797	-111770.37	-111770.37	-111770.37	0.0001	0.0001
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	1798	-106915.79	-106915.70	-106915.79	0.1816	0.0004
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	1798	-105792.26	-105774.49	-105792.26	35.5274	0.0000
<i>A. cristatellus</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	1798	-107373.59	-107373.57	-107373.59	0.0332	0.0001
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. cuvieri</i>	1798	-108135.19	-108135.19	-108135.19	-0.0079	0.0000
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	1795	-82697.69	-82696.49	-82696.48	2.3999	2.4301
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	1798	-94842.43	-94842.66	-94842.44	-0.4473	-0.0224
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	1797	-92308.61	-92308.44	-92308.61	0.3493	0.0029
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	1797	-101043.54	-101043.52	-101043.52	0.0419	0.0421
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	1798	-95171.59	-95171.88	-95171.89	-0.5839	-0.6144
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	1798	-94877.65	-94877.57	-94877.60	0.1650	0.1005
<i>A. cooki</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	1798	-97209.83	-97209.23	-97209.40	1.1930	0.8616
<i>A. cuvieri</i>	<i>A. evermanni</i>	1795	-89633.26	-89633.45	-89633.22	-0.3760	0.0812
<i>A. cuvieri</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	1798	-115523.62	-115523.62	-115523.62	0.0010	0.0028
<i>A. cuvieri</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	1797	-105266.62	-105266.60	-105266.59	0.0509	0.0657
<i>A. cuvieri</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	1797	-108425.50	-108425.62	-108425.50	-0.2397	0.0000
<i>A. cuvieri</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	1797	-114405.14	-114406.49	-114405.12	-2.6838	0.0456
<i>A. cuvieri</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	1798	-117312.07	-117312.39	-117311.99	-0.6429	0.1676

Taxon 1	Taxon 2	N[loci]	$M_0 \ln L$ (no gene flow)	$M_1 \ln L$ (discrete-beta)	$M_2 \ln L$ (isolation- migration)	M_1-M_0 $2\Delta \ln L$	M_2-M_0 $2\Delta \ln L$
<i>A. cuvieri</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	1798	-114172.50	-114172.50	-114172.50	-0.0046	0.0015
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. gundlachi</i>	1795	-82973.84	-82973.90	-82973.88	-0.1091	-0.0183
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	1794	-84494.28	-84494.59	-84494.29	-0.6126	0.1558
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	1794	-94845.19	-94845.19	-94845.46	-0.0019	-0.5454
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	1795	-85497.84	-85498.58	-85497.62	-1.4645	0.4501
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	1795	-81239.64	-81239.89	-81241.46	-0.5047	-3.6291
<i>A. evermanni</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	1795	-75614.61	-75615.11	-75614.70	-1.0036	-0.1760
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. krugi</i>	1797	-94791.11	-94791.08	-94791.71	0.0689	-1.1927
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	1797	-107760.60	-107760.60	107760.60	0.0000	0.0000
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	1798	-96515.10	-96515.50	-96515.03	-0.7961	0.1495
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	1798	-97683.08	-97662.98	-97683.08	40.1926	0.0000
<i>A. gundlachi</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	1798	-100217.91	-100217.80	-100217.87	0.2173	0.0780
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. occultus</i>	1796	-103263.92	-103263.41	-103263.41	1.0185	1.0185
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	1797	-95563.20	-95563.18	-95563.62	0.0285	-0.8411
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	1797	-92909.40	-92909.30	-92909.30	0.1998	0.2038
<i>A. krugi</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	1797	-96542.88	-96542.89	-96542.90	-0.0101	-0.0230
<i>A. occultus</i>	<i>A. poncensis</i>	1797	-107440.69	-107440.69	-107440.69	0.0032	0.0057
<i>A. occultus</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	1797	-107361.10	-107361.10	-107361.10	0.0000	0.0000
<i>A. occultus</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	1797	-105593.09	-105592.91	-105592.91	0.3535	0.3542
<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. pulchellus</i>	1798	-98858.09	-98858.06	-98858.09	0.0500	0.0047
<i>A. poncensis</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	1798	-102626.07	-102626.13	-102626.10	-0.1091	-0.0598
<i>A. pulchellus</i>	<i>A. stratulus</i>	1798	-103446.94	-103446.94	-103446.94	0.0017	0.0035

Table S6: F-tests of transgressive evolution. We tested hypotheses of homogenous (H_1) and heterogeneous (H_2) trait shifts immediately following inferred hybridization events compared to a null hypothesis of no trait shift (32).

	H_1			H_2		
	R^2	F	p	R^2	F	p
Snout-Vent Length	0.919	4.672	0.136	0.930	1.072	0.419
Head Length	0.988	26.178	0.009	0.991	2.191	0.261
Femur Length	0.808	0.010	0.922	0.811	0.094	0.853
Toepad Width	0.904	15.099	0.023	0.980	4.639	0.136
Tail Length	0.165	6.128	0.128	0.445	3.540	0.170